

**INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

Shodmonova Munira Burkhanovna

munira100@mail.ru

Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, senior teacher of the Department of Uzbek language education in Uzga- speaking groups, doctor of philosophy (PhD) in pedagogy

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ANNOTATION

To establish the independent education of teachers of mother tongue and literature from the modular educational type of pedagogical technology in advanced training courses, to provide them with certain educational materials until advanced training, and to monitor their activities after the **course** . It is appropriate to use it for the purpose of organization.

Key words: Modular education, small module, primary module, pedagogical technology, technological map;

JG Yoldoshev and S. Hasanov [78; 547-p.] opinions expressed by scientists are of great importance. As you know, modules include concepts such as submodule, set of modules , primary module, and module level. A small module is the smallest unit in the pedagogical technology and cannot be divided into other small modules that make up this module.

Modules of modern pedagogical technology are divided into the following levels ;

- one training session ;
- department , part or all of the educational subject and teaching technology;
- the components of DTS and the technology of ensuring their implementation;
- up the structural parts of curriculum and programs and the technology of ensuring their implementation;
- modules that make up educational tools;
- modules that organize the methods used in the process of modern pedagogical technologies .

the module is not an immutable , frozen thing, but different ways, methods, and tools can be used that ensure its full implementation without changing the goal set in the module, "Literature" We have shown the module of the lesson on the topic of "development and design of the technological map of the lesson" in the following form:

A lesson module on the topic of developing and designing a technological map of a lesson in literature				
A small module	Didactic purpose of the module	Assignments on the material that listeners should master	Instructions for completing the task	Grade
1	2	3	4	5

1-KM	To determine the audience's knowledge of the subject based on questions and answers	<p>Questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What do you pay attention to when creating developments for literature classes? 1. What do you mainly reflect in the techno-logic map of the lesson? 1. Do you have lesson planning skills? 	Read the questions carefully and write down 3 main ideas that are important to you for each question.	
2-KM	<p>The purpose of the lesson, type, method, method, equipment, tools, organization of the educational process, lesson process, lesson plan, expected result:</p> <p>Gain an understanding of 'design'.</p>	<p>What should be considered when setting lesson goals ?</p> <p>What is the importance of methods, methods and tools in the teaching process?</p> <p>Are there differences in the organization of the educational process and the teaching process ?</p> <p>What result do you expect from the literature lesson?</p> <p>What is design?</p> <p>What forms do you know?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compare the sample technological map in your hands with the technological logical map that you will develop in class . 2. In a pair with your right-hand colleague, identify 7 factors that have a positive effect on the effectiveness of the lesson. 	
3-KM	Expanding the audience's knowledge level, ability to focus on information and to sort out what is important	Read the theoretical information given on the development and design of the technological map of the lesson and form a short vocabulary	Work independently.	
4-KM	To develop the professional training of native language and literature teachers, to encourage a creative approach to lessons.	<p>Through prose works.</p> <p>Based on dramatic works.</p> <p>With the help of poetic works.</p> <p>Through epics, etc</p>	Develop a lesson module on a specific topic in literature with your group.	
5-KM	Clarification and improvement of the given knowledge on a new topic	For example, design, technological map, lesson objective, method, method, expected result, etc	Write in your notebook 2 terms that you remembered during the lesson. Don't repeat what your predecessors have said.	

6-KM	Complete the module. To know the audience's opinion on the module program.	Homework: If you make a mistake in your activity, repeat it using the module program . Work out a technological map of the lesson based on the topic covered.	Tell us what you think about the module program.	
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Figure 1. Lesson module on the topic "Development and design of the technological map of the lesson in literature".

At the same time, modular education allows remote training of students. To teachers of mother tongue and literature learning materials are delivered in the form of individual modules via a computer network. After the teachers have fully studied the materials, assignments (exercises) are sent for independent assessment and further strengthening of the acquired theoretical knowledge. Information about new sites created in the field of literature is also provided .

Collaborative education takes into account the joint activity of pedagogues and students in the process of educational activity, development, deep understanding of each other, mutual emotional closeness, joint analysis of the stages of activity and the results achieved in them, advanced , is of particular importance with its developing ideas. Cooperative education is based on the following target directions:

- organization of relations based on educational cooperation in accordance with pedagogical goals;
- individual approach to the listener based on humanitarian ideas ;
- achieving professional and spiritual unity in the educational process.

idea of co-operative education is to complete educational tasks together and to learn together. In such an educational technology, it is necessary to pay attention to the correct performance of tasks by the listener in cooperation with his partner and to the creation of educational activity in each member of the group. Most importantly, collaborative pedagogy empowers both the teacher and the student . Everyone will think about the consequences of their actions. We used collaborative learning in our pilot work based on three stages:

prepare for the organization of the educational process , in which the participants are studied in advance, alternative methods suitable for possible problematic situations are considered, equipment and space are prepared.

working out ways to solve the problem with the participation of the group and choosing the best ones) .

3rd stage - analysis of the educational process and its results, drawing a conclusion.

training , which is always mentioned when talking about professional development, has a special importance in the formation of the following skills and competencies of teachers of mother tongue and literature in terms of organizing lessons:

- maintaining the necessary training-methodical documents (work plan, report);
- to determine the personality qualities of students ;
- students in the spirit of national values;

- inculcating good manners and virtues in the students through the image of the characters in the work;
- think of measures to eliminate problematic situations encountered in the course of the lesson ;
- for increasing the efficiency of the educational process ;
- ways out of unexpected situations with educational subjects, team members and others ;
- students to certain professions or trades based on taking into account their interests, abilities and skills;
- effective educational methods and advanced pedagogical technologies in professional activities;
- organization of trainings that help to effectively organize interpersonal relations and native language and literature classes, to develop the professional training of native language and literature teachers .

Another method that ensures the effectiveness of education, which is widely used in the process of professional development, is the subject of **many debates** in practice. is being used. Indeed, the debates ensure the mutual exchange of experiences of teachers of mother tongue and literature, enrich their theoretical knowledge and familiarize them with the achievements achieved in the field and advanced pedagogical technologies .

To increase the effectiveness of the discussion method, it should be organized in small groups. This allows active participation of each listener. The listener will have the opportunity to gain a deep understanding of the aspects that he needs to pay attention to in the organization of native language and literature classes , to get acquainted with the methods that guarantee the effectiveness of the lesson, to study new literature created in recent years in the fields of pedagogy and methodology. The organization of discussions on a specific topic directs the activity of listeners to a specific goal . When organizing such an exercise, the leader (trainer or androgygist-pedagogue, active listener or invited expert) formulates questions on the topic for discussion, develops an approximate draft of the exercise, anticipates the opinions of the audience and prepares a thesis. This ensures the orderly course of debates, not deviating from the topic, distinguishing the important ones from the opinions expressed and coming to a single conclusion based on them.

the teachers of the mother tongue and literature have certain theoretical knowledge and practical experience about the educational process and the methods of organizing it according to the purpose ensures the effective course of the debates . After all, the entity organizing the debate does not give any information, instructions or advice about ways to find a solution to the problem. it is entirely up to the listeners to find a solution , and they work independently for this purpose. The presenter can encourage only where necessary , encourage the audience to be active or ask the next question. According to this feature, the debate can be compared to a small research aimed at finding a theoretical solution to a specific problem.

The improvement of technical means created the basis for the expansion of the scope of using their services . Today, the use of various information technologies and modern technical devices in the educational process has become a habit. **Video analysis** allows to re-study specific events related to the content of a training with the help of images, to analyze the

situation in detail . Video analysis , which is an element of problem-based education, is effective in introducing students to the best practices in understanding the content of interpersonal relationships, solving problem situations, and organizing native language and literature classes. For video analysis , educational programs, slide films, and clips illustrating the work experiences of native language and literature teachers are selected. Video analysis can also be used to evaluate the content and results of training, role- plays , and debates. It is better to use video analysis in the course of professional development with mass (course) or group participation .

In the process of qualification improvement, introducing native language and literature teachers to current pedagogical and methodical problems, research results, best practices in the organization of native language and literature classes, **presentation to ensure the teacher's learning and development (or it is advisable to use the protection) method.** It has been proven in the experiment that the performance of the defense of the students' qualification work at the end of the course in the form of such a presentation will give a good result . This method develops creative approach to organizing their professional activities and independent learning skills in native language and literature teachers . When using the presentation or defense method , it is possible to clearly demonstrate and explain the essence of the problem, its solution, and related recommendations by expressing it in different forms of tables, diagrams, images, pictures, symbols, and other forms.

Game technologies means the use of didactic games in the educational process. They can generally be divided into role-playing and business games . In the process of studying the possibilities and essence of the game in improving the professional skills of native language and literature teachers, it was found that business games are not so effective. Therefore, role-playing games were mainly used in the organization of training in the courses.

Role- playing games help teachers of mother tongue and literature to master the skills and competencies of effective lesson planning. By performing different roles, the participants of the educational process will have the opportunity to solve pedagogical, psychological, methodical problems, to fully understand the theoretical knowledge necessary for teachers of mother tongue and literature, and to think about problems that have received little attention before. For example, a role -playing game serves to illuminate various problems or situations encountered in educational practice through scenes and role-playing actions. Through role-playing , students gain a deeper understanding of the nature of pedagogical problems or situations.

role -playing games, to familiarize the audience with the essence and conditions of role-playing games; taking into account their capabilities and professional abilities when assigning roles; determine the time of the game in advance and inform the participants; ensure the full participation of the whole group in the game; native language and literature teacher to evaluate the importance of using role-playing games and predict the expected result. In the organization of the educational process with the help of role-playing games, it is necessary to pay attention to such things as careful preparation in terms of content and organization, ensuring the logic and vitality of problems, correct distribution of roles according to the potential of participants, and purposeful preparation of role-playing situations in advance . . Of course, it is necessary to use the method of professional role- playing games very carefully in the training system .

References:

1. Ishmuhamedov R., Abdukadirov A., Pardaev A. Innovative technologies in education (practical recommendations for pedagogues-teachers of educational institutions).-T.: "Talent" Foundation, 2008 -180 p.
2. M. Shodmonova. Advanced foreign experiences in education. Study guide. Tashkent: 2022.
3. M. Shodmonova. Teacher skill: factors that develop it. Monograph. - Moldova, 2022. 1 41 p.
4. Z. Takhirov, S. Muhamedova, G. Asilova, M. Shodmonova. Reflection of a Subjective Approach in Lexical, Semantic Means of Artistic Speech. PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION (2021) 58(1): 2011-2017.
5. <http://elibrary.ru>. Historical and methodological aspects of the formation of language skills and pedagogy